

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Instability Tendencies in A Three Species Ecological Model with Distributed Time Delay

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Abstract

Objectives: The stability analysis of three species ecological model with distributed time delay was investigated. The Hopf bifurcation analysis is discussed using the weight kernel which is also taken as bifurcation parameter.

Methods: This study has formulated the mathematical model using system of integro differential equations. The well posed-ness of the model is studied. The linear stability and global stability of the model is discussed. Numerical simulation is carried out using MATLAB to identify the kernel weights. **Findings:** This study has proved that the solutions are positive and bounded in R_3^+ . The co-existing state is identified for the proposed model. The linear stability analysis is studied at the co-existing state and proved that the system is locally asymptotically stable. The global stability analysis is established by constructing suitable Lyapunov's function and proved that the system is globally asymptotically stable. Hopf bifurcation analysis is studied using numerical simulation. This study identifies the range of kernel strengths, at which the system exhibits the Hopf bifurcation nature. It is concluded that the kernel weights are influential in the dynamics of the model, which leads to the instability tendencies. **Novelty:** The Hopf bifurcation analysis of distributed time delay model using kernel dynamics is first of its kind. So far, theoretical results have been furnished, and no significant contribution made in this area. The authors elaborated the significance of kernel weights, which are instrumental in the dynamics of the model. The critical values of kernel weights which change the behaviour of the system from stable equilibrium to unstable equilibrium. The Hopf bifurcation analysis is addressed using these weight kernels.

Keywords: Prey; Predator; Competitor; Co-existing state; Stability analysis; Hopf bifurcation

1 Introduction

The elegance of nature is explained using mathematical methods and is prominent in the recent era. Mathematicians are attracted to study the ecological and biological phenomenon. Differential equations are pioneering in this field. Keeping Natural resources in harmony, an entire ecological phenomenon is in balance. The study of ecological balance in terms of stability analysis was studied using differential equations. The basic population growth models using differential equations are initiated by Lokta and Volterra.

Prey-predator interactions are universal biological relationship in ecology. This relation attracted the attention of many biologists and mathematicians. The prey predator dynamics with fractional order differential equations and Hopf bifurcation analytics are well versed by Ruizhi Yang⁽¹⁾. The memory effect in predator and fear effect in prey species and its global dynamics was dealt by Nadjah K⁽²⁾. The harvesting of ecological resources is extensively studied during this era. Recently Jiao Jiang⁽³⁾ explored the dynamics of bio-economic model with Michaelis mention type harvesting in prey species and conclude that over harvesting leads to the bifurcation. Chen H⁽⁴⁾ studied the Hopf bifurcation analysis of diffusive prey-predator system. Wie Liu⁽⁵⁾ explore the direction of Hopf bifurcation in the Gause type prey-predator model with Michaelis-mention type harvesting. Ranjith Kumar G⁽⁶⁾ discussed the crowding effects and its mechanics in prey-predator model with inter specific competition rates. Recently Paparao A V^(7,8) explored the harvesting efforts with constant effort and Michaelis mention in two compartment prey-predator model and shown that the system is globally asymptotically stable.

In any ecological and biological phenomenon time delays are inevitable. Time delays mainly classified as discrete, continuous and distributed type. The time delay term can be introduced in prey, predator and into the interaction of prey and predator terms. The time lags in the three species models exhibits rich dynamics. The dynamics of one prey and two predators with a discrete time lag in the interaction of prey-predator species dealt by Paparao A V⁽⁹⁾ and identified Hopf bifurcation phenomenon by taking the bifurcation parameter as ' τ' '.

The distributed time lags in the three species models in the interaction of two mutualistic species was dealt by Paparao A V⁽¹⁰⁻¹⁴⁾. It is observed that the system is asymptotically stable, and no bifurcation tendency exist. Similarly, the distributed time lags in three species model with prey, predator and ammensal was dealt by Paparao A V^(11,12) and shown that the model does not exhibits Hopf bifurcation behaviour. Paparao A V⁽¹³⁾ discussed the time delay model which exhibits Hopf bifurcation. The discrete time lag ' τ' ' was taken as Hopf bifurcation parameter. The critical values of ' τ' ' are identified using numerical simulation which cause the instability tendencies in this model. The distributed time delay model with a prey, predator and ammensal model was dealt by Paparao A V⁽¹⁴⁾ and observed the Hopf bifurcation tendency. The critical values of the model are identified using weight kernels as bifurcation parameter. The stability aspects of system elaborated with distributed time lags and studied the local and global dynamics at equilibrium points. The system is asymptotically stable at co-existing state and the results are driven by numerical simulation with different delay kernel strengths as bifurcation parameter.

The Hopf bifurcation tendencies in distributed type delay models are quite interesting. So far this type of analysis was not considered. Despite these models, we proposed a three species model of distributed time delay with a prey, predator and competitor. The dynamics of the model and instability criteria was discussed. The Hopf bifurcation analysis is studied by taking exponential kernel as weight function and parameter ' λ' ' taken as bifurcation parameter. The critical values using numerical simulation were illustrated in Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2 the model formation and properties like bounded-ness and existence of positive solutions, in section3 we discuss equilibrium point, in local stability analysis, global stability analysis, finally numerical simulation is carried out in support of Hopf bifurcation analysis, conclusion is in section 4 and references is in section 5.

2 Methodology

In this section we propose the mathematical model and studied the bounded-ness property and existence positive solutions of the model.

2.1. Formation of Mathematical model

The proposed ecosystem with three species namely prey (N_1), predator (N_2) and competitor (N_3). The competitor species is competing for both prey and predator. A distributed time lag is induced in the prey and predator species. An exponential growth is included in all three species.

Based on these considerations, the ecosystem is expressed as the following system of integro-differential equations.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_1}{dt} &= a_1N_1 - \alpha_{11}N_1^2 - \alpha_{12}N_1 \int_{-\infty}^t k_1(t-u)N_2(u)du - \alpha_{13}N_1N_3 \\ \frac{dN_2}{dt} &= a_2N_2 - \alpha_{22}N_2^2 - \alpha_{21}N_2 \int_{-\infty}^t k_2(t-u)N_1(u)du - \alpha_{23}N_2N_3 \\ \frac{dN_3}{dt} &= a_3N_3 - \alpha_{33}N_3^2 - \alpha_{31}N_1N_3 - \alpha_{32}N_3N_2 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1.1}$$

Nomenclature:

- $N_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$: Prey, predator and competitor populations
 - $a_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$: Growth rate of prey, predator and competitor population
 - $\alpha_{ii} (i = 1, 2, 3)$: Inter specific competition rate of three populations
 - $\alpha_{ij} : (i \neq j)$: Interaction coefficient among three species
 - $k_1(t-u) \& k_2(t-u)$: Kernel strengths
- Put $t-u = z$, in the Equation (2.1.1) we get the following system of equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_1}{dt} &= a_1N_1 - \alpha_{11}N_1^2 - \alpha_{12}N_1 \int_0^\infty k_1(z)N_2(t-z)dz - \alpha_{13}N_1N_3 \\ \frac{dN_2}{dt} &= a_2N_2 - \alpha_{22}N_2^2 + \alpha_{21}N_2 \int_0^\infty k_2(z)N_1(t-z)dz - \alpha_{23}N_2N_3 \\ \frac{dN_3}{dt} &= a_3N_3 - \alpha_{33}N_3^2 - \alpha_{31}N_1N_3 - \alpha_{32}N_3N_2 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1.2}$$

Choose the kernels k_1 and k_2 such that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^\infty k_1(z)dz &= 1, \int_0^\infty k_2(z)dz = 1, \\ \int_0^\infty zk_1(z)dz &< \infty, \& \int_0^\infty zk_2(z)dz < \infty \end{aligned} \tag{2.1.3}$$

Assuming the solutions for the above model Equation (2.1.2) as

$$N_1 = A_1e^{\lambda t}, N_2 = A_2e^{\lambda t}, N_3 = A_3e^{\lambda t}$$

The system Equation (2.1.1) transform in to

$$\begin{aligned} N_1' &= a_1N_1 - \alpha_{11}N_1^2 - \alpha_{12}N_1N_2k_1(\lambda) - \alpha_{13}N_1N_3 \\ N_2' &= a_2N_2 - \alpha_{22}N_2^2 + \alpha_{21}N_1N_2k_2(\lambda) - \alpha_{23}N_2N_3 \\ N_3' &= a_3N_3 - \alpha_{33}N_3^2 - \alpha_{31}N_1N_3 - \alpha_{32}N_2N_3 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1.4}$$

Here $k_1(\lambda)$ is the Laplace transform of $k_1(z)$ and $k_2(\lambda)$ is the Laplace transform of $k_2(z)$.

2.2. Existence of positive solutions and bounded-ness property

In this section we proved that the system of Equation (2.1.1) admits positive solutions and are also bounded.

Theorem 2.2.1: The system of Equation (2.1.1) possesses positive solutions in R_3^+

Proof: From the system of Equation (2.1.4) we can write as follows

$$\begin{aligned} N_1(t) &= N_{10}e^{\int_0^t (a_1 - \alpha_{11}N_1 - \alpha_{12}N_2k_1(\lambda) - \alpha_{13}N_3)dt} > 0 \\ N_2(t) &= N_{20}e^{\int_0^t (a_2 - \alpha_{22}N_2 + \alpha_{21}N_1k_2(\lambda) - \alpha_{23}N_3)dt} > 0 \\ N_3(t) &= N_{30}e^{\int_0^t (a_3 - \alpha_{33}N_3 - \alpha_{31}N_1 - \alpha_{32}N_2)dt} > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, all the solutions are positive in R_3^+ .

Theorem 2.2.2: The solutions of the system of Equation (2.1.1) are bounded.

Proof: From the system of Equation (2.1.4) can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} N_1' &\leq \{a_1 N_1 - \alpha_{11} N_1^2\} \\ N_2' &\leq \{a_2 N_2 - \alpha_{22} N_2^2\} \\ N_3 &\leq \{a_3 N_3 - \alpha_{33} N_3^2\} \end{aligned} \tag{2.2.2.1}$$

By solving the above equations, we can write as

$$N_1(t) \leq \frac{a_1}{\alpha_{11} + ke^{-a_1 t}}, N_2(t) \leq \frac{a_2}{\alpha_{22} + ke^{-a_2 t}}, \text{ and } N_3(t) \leq \frac{a_3}{\alpha_{33} + ke^{-a_3 t}} \tag{2.2.2.2}$$

From the above Equation (2.2.2.2), it is evident that the system of Equation (2.1.1) possesses bounded solutions.

3 Results and Discussion

In this section we identify the co-existing state and studied the stability analysis both locally and globally this point. We also performed numerical simulation to illustrate the analytical results and Hopf bifurcation analysis.

3.1. Equilibrium point

The co-existing state is obtained by equating $\frac{dN_i}{dt} = 0, i = 1, 2, 3$ from the system given as follows

E: Co-existing state:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_1 &= \frac{a_1 (\alpha_{22}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{23}\alpha_{32}) - \alpha_{12}k_1(\lambda) (a_2\alpha_{33} - a_3\alpha_{23}) + \alpha_{13} (a_2\alpha_{32} - a_3\alpha_{22})}{\alpha_{11} (\alpha_{22}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{23}\alpha_{32}) + \alpha_{12}k_1(\lambda) (\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{33} + \alpha_{31}\alpha_{23}) - \alpha_{13} (\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{31}\alpha_{22})} \\ \bar{N}_2 &= \frac{(a_2\alpha_{11}\alpha_{33} + a_1\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{33} + a_1\alpha_{31}\alpha_{23}) - (a_3\alpha_{11}\alpha_{23} + a_3\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{13} + a_2\alpha_{13}\alpha_{31})}{\alpha_{11} (\alpha_{22}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{23}\alpha_{32}) + \alpha_{12}k_1(\lambda) (\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{33} + \alpha_{31}\alpha_{23}) - \alpha_{13} (\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{31}\alpha_{22})} \\ \bar{N}_3 &= \frac{(a_3\alpha_{11}\alpha_{22} + a_3\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{12}k_1(\lambda) + a_2\alpha_{12}k_1(\lambda)\alpha_{31}) - (a_2\alpha_{11}\alpha_{32} + a_1\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{32} + a_1\alpha_{31}\alpha_{22})}{\alpha_{11} (\alpha_{22}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{23}\alpha_{32}) + \alpha_{12}k_1(\lambda) (\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{33} + \alpha_{31}\alpha_{23}) - \alpha_{13} (\alpha_{21}k_2(\lambda)\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{31}\alpha_{22})} \end{aligned}$$

This equilibrium state exists only when,

$$\bar{N}_1 > 0, \bar{N}_2 > 0, \bar{N}_3 > 0 \tag{3.1.1}$$

3.2. Linear Stability analysis at the co-existing state

Theorem 3.2.1: The co-existing state $E(\bar{N}_1, \bar{N}_2, \bar{N}_3)$ is locally asymptotically stable if $\alpha_{11}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{13}\alpha_{31} > 0$

Proof: The variational matrix is given by

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} -\alpha_{11}\bar{N}_1 & -\alpha_{12}\bar{N}_1k_1(\lambda) & -\alpha_{13}\bar{N}_1 \\ \alpha_{21}\bar{N}_2k_2(\lambda) & -\alpha_{22}\bar{N}_2 & -\alpha_{23}\bar{N}_2 \\ -\alpha_{31}\bar{N}_3 & -\alpha_{32}\bar{N}_3 & -\alpha_{33}\bar{N}_3 \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.2.1}$$

With the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^3 + b_1\lambda^2 + b_2\lambda + b_3 = 0 \tag{3.2.2}$$

Here

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= (\alpha_{11}\bar{N}_1 + \alpha_{22}\bar{N}_2 + \alpha_{33}\bar{N}_3) \\ b_2 &= (\alpha_{11}\alpha_{22} + \alpha_{12}\alpha_{21}k_1(\lambda)k_2(\lambda))\bar{N}_1\bar{N}_2 + (\alpha_{11}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{13}\alpha_{31})\bar{N}_1\bar{N}_3 \\ &\quad + (\alpha_{22}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{23}\alpha_{32})\bar{N}_2\bar{N}_3 \\ b_3 &= \bar{N}_1\bar{N}_2\bar{N}_3(\alpha_{11}\alpha_{22}\alpha_{33} + \alpha_{12}\alpha_{21}\alpha_{33}k_1(\lambda)k_2(\lambda) \\ &\quad - \alpha_{13}\alpha_{22}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{11}\alpha_{23}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{12}\alpha_{23}\alpha_{31}k_1(\lambda) + \alpha_{13}\alpha_{21}\alpha_{32}k_2(\lambda)) \end{aligned} \tag{3.2.3}$$

By Routh-Hurwitz criteria, the system is stable if $b_1 > 0$, $(b_1 b_2 - b_3) > 0$ and $b_3(b_1 b_2 - b_3) > 0$

Clearly $b_1 = (\alpha_{11} \bar{N}_1 + \alpha_{22} \bar{N}_2 + \alpha_{33} \bar{N}_3) > 0$

Calculate the following

$$\begin{aligned}
 (b_1 b_2 - b_3) &= (\alpha_{11}^2 \alpha_{22} + \alpha_{11} \alpha_{12} \alpha_{21} k_1(\lambda) k_2(\lambda)) \bar{N}_1^2 \bar{N}_2 + (\alpha_{11}^2 \alpha_{33} - \alpha_{11} \alpha_{13} \alpha_{31}) \bar{N}_1^2 \bar{N}_3 \\
 &+ (\alpha_{22}^2 \alpha_{33} + \alpha_{22} \alpha_{23} \alpha_{32}) \bar{N}_2^2 \bar{N}_3 + (\alpha_{22}^2 \alpha_{11} + \alpha_{22} \alpha_{12} \alpha_{21} k_1(\lambda) k_2(\lambda)) \bar{N}_2^2 \bar{N}_1 \\
 &+ (\alpha_{11} \alpha_{33}^2 - \alpha_{33} \alpha_{13} \alpha_{31}) \bar{N}_3^2 \bar{N}_1 + (\alpha_{22} \alpha_{33}^2 + \alpha_{33} \alpha_{23} \alpha_{32}) \bar{N}_3^2 \bar{N}_2 \\
 &+ \bar{N}_1 \bar{N}_2 \bar{N}_3 (2\alpha_{11} \alpha_{22} \alpha_{33} + \alpha_{12} \alpha_{23} \alpha_{31} k_1(\lambda) + \alpha_{13} \alpha_{21} \alpha_{32} k_2(\lambda))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$(b_1 b_2 - b_3) > 0 \text{ if } \alpha_{11} \alpha_{33} - \alpha_{13} \alpha_{31} > 0 \tag{3.2.4}$$

Also $b_3(b_1 b_2 - b_3) > 0$ if $\alpha_{11} \alpha_{33} - \alpha_{13} \alpha_{31} > 0$.

Hence, the co-existing state $E(\bar{N}_1, \bar{N}_2, \bar{N}_3)$ is locally asymptotically stable if

$$\alpha_{11} \alpha_{33} - \alpha_{13} \alpha_{31} > 0.$$

3.3. Global Stability

Theorem 3.3.1: The co-existing state $E(\bar{N}_1, \bar{N}_2, \bar{N}_3)$ is globally asymptotically stable.

Proof: We considered the Lyapunov’s function as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V(\bar{N}_1, \bar{N}_2, \bar{N}_3) &= \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i - \bar{N}_i - \bar{N}_i \log\left(\frac{N_i}{\bar{N}_i}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} \int_0^\infty k_1(z) \int_{t-z}^t [N_2 - \bar{N}_2]^2 \, dudz \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} \int_0^\infty k_2(z) \int_{t-z}^t [N_1 - \bar{N}_1]^2 \, dudz
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3.1}$$

The time derivate of ‘V’ along with the solutions of Equation (2.1.2) is

$$\begin{aligned}
 V^1(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^3 \left[\frac{N_i - \bar{N}_i}{N_i} N_i^1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} \int_0^\infty k_1(z) [N_2 - \bar{N}_2]^2 \, dz - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} \int_0^\infty k_1(z) [N_2(t-z) - \bar{N}_2]^2 \, dz \right. \\
 &\left. + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} \int_0^\infty k_2(z) [N_1 - \bar{N}_1]^2 \, dz - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} \int_0^\infty k_2(z) [N_1(t-z) - \bar{N}_1]^2 \, dz \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3.2}$$

From the Equation (3.3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 V'(t) &= [N_1 - \bar{N}_1] (a_1 - \alpha_{11} N_1 - \alpha_{12} \int_0^\infty k_1(z) N_2(t-z) \, dz - \alpha_{13} N_3 + [N_2 - \bar{N}_2] \\
 &(a_2 - \alpha_{22} N_2 + \alpha_{21} \int_0^\infty k_2(z) N_1(t-z) \, dz - \alpha_{23}) + [N_3 - \bar{N}_3] (a_3 - \alpha_{33} N_3 - \alpha_{31} N_1 - \alpha_{32} N_2) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} [N_2 - \bar{N}_2]^2 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} [N_1 - \bar{N}_1]^2 - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} \int_0^\infty k_1(z) [N_2(t-z) - \bar{N}_2]^2 \, dz \\
 &- \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} \int_0^\infty k_2(z) [N_1(t-z) - \bar{N}_1]^2 \, dz
 \end{aligned}$$

By proper choice of a_1, a_2 & a_3 and using the inequality $ab \leq \frac{a^2+b^2}{2}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^\infty k_1(z) [N_2(t-z) - \bar{N}_2]^2 \, dz &\leq \int_0^\infty k_1(z) \, dz = 1 \text{ and} \\
 \int_0^\infty k_2(z) [N_1(t-z) - \bar{N}_1]^2 \, dz &\leq \int_0^\infty k_2(z) \, dz = 1 \\
 &= -\alpha_{11} (N_1 - \bar{N}_1)^2 - \alpha_{22} (N_2 - \bar{N}_2)^2 - \alpha_{33} (N_3 - \bar{N}_3)^2 - \frac{(\alpha_{13} + \alpha_{31})}{2} [(N_1 - \bar{N}_1)^2 + (N_3 - \bar{N}_3)^2] \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} [N_1 - \bar{N}_1]^2 - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} [N_2 - \bar{N}_2]^2 + \frac{(\alpha_{23} + \alpha_{32})}{2} [(N_2 - \bar{N}_2)^2 + (N_3 - \bar{N}_3)^2] - \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_{12} + \alpha_{21}) \\
 &\leq -|(\alpha_{11} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{31} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12})| (N_1 - \bar{N}_1)^2 - |(\alpha_{22} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{12} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{21} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{32} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{23})| (N_2 - \bar{N}_2)^2 \\
 &\quad - |(\alpha_{33} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{13} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{32} - \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{23})| (N_3 - \bar{N}_3)^2 - \frac{1}{2} ((\alpha_{12} + \alpha_{21})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow V'(t) \leq -\mu \sum_{i=1}^3 [N_i - \bar{N}_i]^2 < 0$$

$$\mu = \min(\alpha_{11} + \alpha_{22} + \alpha_{33} + \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{13} + \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{31} + \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{21} - \frac{1}{2}\alpha_{12} - \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_{23} + \alpha_{32}))$$

Therefore, the system is globally stable at the co-existing state $E_2(\bar{N}_1, \bar{N}_2, \bar{N}_3)$.

3.4. Numerical Simulation:

Example 3.4.1: Let $a_1=1.5, a_2=2.65, a_3=3.45, \alpha_{11}=0.1, \alpha_{12}=0.5, \alpha_{13}=0.01, \alpha_{21}=0.5, \alpha_{22}=0.2, \alpha_{23}=0.4, \alpha_{31}=0.2, \alpha_{32}=0.2, \alpha_{33}=0.2, N_1=10, N_2=15, N_3=15$.

The systems of Equation (2.1.2) with exponential delay kernel weights $k_1(z) = k_2(z) = ae^{-az}$ for $a > 0$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} N_1' &= a_1 N_1 - \alpha_{11} N_1^2 - \alpha_{12} N_1 N_2 \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + a} - \alpha_{13} N_1 N_3 \\ N_2' &= a_2 N_2 - \alpha_{22} N_2^2 + \alpha_{21} N_1 N_2 \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + a} - \alpha_{23} N_2 N_3 \\ N_3' &= a_3 N_3 - \alpha_{33} N_3^2 + \alpha_{31} N_1 N_3 - \alpha_{32} N_2 N_3 \end{aligned} \tag{3.4.1}$$

The system of Equation (3.4.1) is simulated using the parametric values shown in example (Equation (3.4.1)) with different kernel strengths λ & a are shown below. Three possible values of λ and values are shown below in which Hopf bifurcation is observed. The time series plot is represented by odd numbers and phase plane plot by even numbers.

Case (i): for $\lambda=0.005, a= 1$

Fig 1.

Fig 2.

The kernel strengths (λ & a) are taken as bifurcation parameters. For $\lambda=0.005, a=1$, the system exhibits unbounded oscillations in three populations. The nature of the system exhibits unbounded oscillations for fixed Values of $\lambda=0.005$ and the range of a is $[1-100]$ is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

For $\lambda=0.005, a=0.001 E(3, 14, 0)$:

Fig 3.

Fig 4.

The unbounded oscillations become stable for $\lambda=0.005$ and a value in $[0.0001, 0.0015]$. The system exhibits switch over behaviour for $a > 0.0015$ and fixed value of $\lambda=0.005$ and $a > 0.0015$, the stable equilibria becomes unstable equilibria which exhibits Hopf bifurcation shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Case (ii): $\lambda=0.05, a= 0.02$

Fig 5.

Fig 6.

Unbounded oscillation exists for $\lambda=0.05$ and $a=0.02$ with the range of 'a' from $[0.02$ to $100]$. The results are explored in the Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows the unstable nature.

$\lambda=0.05, a= 0.015$

Fig 7.

Fig 8.

The stable oscillations occur for $\lambda=0.05$ and 'a' from range $[0.0001, 0.015]$. Hence, for $\lambda=0.05$ and $a > 0.015$ indicating the qualitative change in system dynamics indicates bifurcation (Figure 7 and Figure 8).

Case (iii): $\lambda=0.5, a= 0.2$

For $\lambda=0.5$ and $a=0.2$, unbounded oscillations exist in the system shows unstable nature shown in (Figure 9 and Figure 10).

Fig 9.

Fig 10.

$$\lambda=0.5, a=0.14 E(5, 9, 4)$$

Fig 11.

The system remains stable for $\lambda=0.5$ and a in the range $[0.0001, 0.15]$. When the value of ' a ' exceeds 0.15 for the fixed $\lambda=0.5$, the stable equilibrium becomes unstable equilibrium which is the evidence for occurrence of Hopf bifurcation (Figure 11 and Figure 12).

Fig 12.

4 Conclusion

In the proposed model the following criteria are well illustrated:

- The well posed-ness of the mathematical model is discussed by studying the existence of positive and bounded solutions. The existence of positive solutions ensure that the dynamics described by the model are nonnegative and bounded-ness ensure the population should not grow indefinitely.
- Local stability criteria is established and proved that the system is locally asymptotically stable at co-existing state if $\alpha_{11}\alpha_{33} - \alpha_{13}\alpha_{31} > 0$. A suitable Lyapunov's function is constructed to prove the global existence of the system.
- Numerical simulation is performed by varying the parameters, especially the strengths of exponential delay kernel weights (λ & a). Different values of these kernel strengths (λ & a) lead to change in the system dynamics between stable and unstable equilibria.
- The critical values of (λ & a) are identified, leading to a Hopf bifurcation. Hopf bifurcation characterizes the qualitative behavior of the system, often involving unbounded oscillation. The switch over behavior is presented below via critical values of the model.

The critical values of (λ & a) for Hopf bifurcation are as follows:

For $\lambda = 0.005$ & $a > 0.0015$, $\lambda = 0.05$ & $a > 0.015$, $\lambda = 0.5$ & $a > 0.15$.

Therefore, the delay arguments are significant to convert the stable equilibria into unstable equilibria. So, the system undergoes Hopf bifurcation for some critical values of λ & a shown as above.

The results are compared with⁽¹⁴⁾ where the model explored the Hopf bifurcation wherein for $\lambda = 0.005$ and $a > 0.02$, $\lambda = 0.05$ & $a > 0.23$, $\lambda = 0.5$ & $a > 2.3$. The time delay is imposed on prey and competitor species. A similarity is identified in this model for fixed value of ' λ ' the value of ' a ' is identified taken as bifurcation parameter. The result with existing literature⁽⁹⁻¹¹⁾ does not exhibits Hopf bifurcation with respect to the bifurcation parameter as kernel weight. Hence, the kernel weights are significant in the dynamics of the proposed model which causes the instability tendencies.

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